

Supplementary Figure 2: Full panel display of fluorescently labeled *B. theta* mutant strains visualized by super-resolution structured illumination microscopy (SR-SIM). Cells are stained with DAPI (blue), FLA-YM or FLA-RGII (green), and Nile Red (red); and displayed at 0* (true zero), 0 (directly after glycan addition), 24 and 72 hours. **(A & B)** Wild-type *B. theta* and mutant Bt Δ MAN1/2/3 cells labeled with FLA-YM. **(C & D)** Wild-type *B. theta* and mutant Bt Δ RGII cells labeled with FLA-RGII. Size bars = 2 μ M.